

SYNTHETIC INVESTIGATIONS ON STEROLS, BILE ACIDS, HORMONES, ETC.
PART III. STUDY OF THE DIECKMANN CONDENSATION PRODUCTS OF THE
TRICARBOXYLIC ESTER OF 2-METHYLPENTANE-1 : 2 : 5-TRICARBOXYLIC
ACID

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Cyclisation product of ethyl 2-methylpentane-1 : 2 : 5-tricarboxylate has been found to be a *cyclopentanone* derivative, as the product obtained by its hydrolysis has been identified with 2-methyl*cyclopentanone*-2-acetic acid.

In a previous communication (Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 453) cyclisation of ethyl 2-methylpentane-1 : 2 : 5-tricarboxylate (I, R=Me) by means of sodium dust in benzene solution had been described. Obviously, hydrolysis of the cyclised product may lead to the formation of two different keto-acids, viz., 2-methyl*cyclopentanone*-2-acetic acid (II, R=R₁=H) and 3-methyl*cyclohexanone*-3-carboxylic acid (III, R=CO₂H), depending upon the manner in which the ring-closure takes place. Actual hydrolysis of the β -ketonic ester was carried out by refluxing with 20% sulphuric acid and the keto-acid, thus obtained, on purification by distillation in vacuum solidified and melted at 68-69°. The semicarbazone of the above keto-acid melts at 202-203°.

In order to determine the constitution of the above keto-acid we have synthesised (II, R=R₁=H) by the following method.

2-Methyl*cyclopentanone* is condensed with ethyl bromoacetate with the aid of sodamide in an ethereal solution (Dutta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 649). The higher boiling condensation product obtained therefrom is condensed with diethyl oxalate in an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide, and the resulting crude glyoxalic ester is pyrolysed to yield ethyl 2-methyl-5-carbethoxycyclopentanone-2-acetate (II, R=C₂H₅, R₁=CO₂C₂H₅). The desired keto-acid (II, R=R₁=H) is obtained by the hydrolysis of the ketonic ester in the usual manner. When the fission of the crude glyoxalic ester is carried out by treatment with an aqueous solution of baryta, the yield of the keto-acid could be further improved. The melting points and the mixed melting points of the above keto-acid and its semicarbazone are found to be identical with those of the keto-acid and the corresponding semicarbazone obtained by the hydrolysis of the cyclised product of (I). The synthesis of the keto-acid (II, R=R₁=H) had previously been described by Robinson and King (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 465) by a similar method but they obtained the acid as a liquid without any purification and in poorer yield and they did not describe any derivative of the above keto-acid. With a view to preparing the keto-acid (III, R=CO₂H), the other possible hydrolysis product of (I, R=Me), we have investigated the addition of hydrogen cyanide to 3-methyl-2-cyclohexenone and under the conditions described, have obtained a moderately good yield of 3-methyl-3-cyanocyclohexanone (III, R=CN).

It is interesting to note in this connection that Perkin and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 2010) carried out the cyclisation of ethyl pentane-1:2:5-tricarboxylate (I, R=H)

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(I)

(II)

(III)

by means of sodium in benzene solution and obtained *cyclohexanone-3-carboxylic acid* by hydrolysis of the cyclised product, the identity of which was proved by an independent synthesis. Later, however, Chatterjee, Das and Barpujari (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 161) observed that ethyl 2-carbethoxycyclopentanone-2-acetate (IV) on boiling in an alcoholic solution with molecular quantity of sodium ethoxide was transformed into ethyl 5-carbethoxycyclopentanone-2-acetate (V), the probable mechanism of the reaction being the alcoholysis to ester (I, R=H) and subsequent ring-closure. The constitution of the ester (V) was established by its hydrolysis to *cyclopentanone-2-acetic acid*. In view of the anomalous results mentioned above, we have repeated the experiments of both sets of workers and our results agree with those of previous workers in every respect.

(IV)

(V)

EXPERIMENTAL

Hydrolysis of the cyclised product of Ethyl 2-Methylpentane-1:2:5 tricarboxylate.—The Dieckmann product (Banerjee, *loc. cit.*, 30 g.) was refluxed with sulphuric acid (20%, 350 c.c.) for 16 hours. The cooled solution was thoroughly extracted with ether after saturation with ammonium sulphate. The ethereal solution was dried over sodium sulphate and ether removed. The residue on distillation boiled at 160°/10 mm. and on standing solidified, m.p. 68-69°. (Found: C, 61.05; H, 7.5. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 61.5; H, 7.7 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* was prepared by warming the keto-acid with a saturated aqueous solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate. On crystallisation from water it melted at 202-203°. (Found: N, 19.1. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires N, 19.7 per cent).

Condensation of 2-Methylcyclopentane with Ethyl Bromoacetate.—2-Methylcyclopentanone (13.8 g.) and finely divided sodamide (6.5 g.) in ether (200 c.c.) were heated under reflux in a three-necked flask fitted with a mercury-sealed mechanical stirrer for 4 hours. The volume of the ethereal solution was then reduced to 100 c.c. The flask was then cooled in ice and water and ethyl bromoacetate (30 g.) was slowly added with stirring. After half an hour the reaction mixture was again refluxed for 1 hour. After cooling water

was added and the ethereal layer separated, washed and dried. After removal of ether a fraction (9 g.) boiling at 125-135°/12 mm. was collected.

2-Methylcyclopentanone-2-acetic Acid.—Diethyl oxalate (4.8 g.) was added to sodium ethoxide solution (from 0.8 g. Na and 10 c.c. absolute alcohol), cooled in a freezing mixture and shaken until a clear solution resulted. 5.7 G. of the above condensation product were then added to it and left overnight. The reaction mixture was then treated with ice-cold distilled water and the neutral material was removed by extraction with water. The aqueous layer after acidification in the cold was thoroughly extracted with ether. After removal of ether the residue was heated at 180-190° with the addition of soft glass powder until the evolution of carbon monoxide ceased, when on distillation 3.5 g. of a product boiling at 162°/6 mm. were obtained.

Hydrolysis of the β -ketonic ester was carried out by refluxing with 20% sulphuric acid (90 c.c.) and the keto-acid was isolated in the usual way. The product on purification by distillation in vacuum solidified, m.p. 66-68°, mixed m.p. 68-69°.

The semicarbazone, prepared in the usual manner, on recrystallisation from water melted at 202-203°.

3-Methyl-3-cyanocyclohexanone.—To a solution of 3-methyl-2-cyclohexanone (11 g.) (Smith and Rouault, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 633) and glacial acetic acid (6 c.c.) in rectified spirit (102 c.c.) cooled in a freezing mixture, was added a solution of potassium cyanide (13 g.) in water (38 c.c.) over a period of half an hour with stirring. The flask was kept at 0° overnight. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and thoroughly extracted with ether after saturation with sodium chloride. Ether was removed and the residue distilled in vacuum. The keto-nitrile (10 g.) was obtained, b.p. 152°/19mm. (Found: C, 69.8; H, 7.9. $C_8H_{11}ON$ requires C, 70.07; H, 8.03 per cent).

The semicarbazone was prepared in the usual manner and after crystallisation from dilute alcohol it melted at 182°. (Found: C, 55.8; H, 7.52. $C_8H_{14}ON_4$ requires C, 55.99; H, 7.21 per cent).

Our thanks are due to Prof. P. C. Mitter for the interest he has taken during the progress of this work and also to Mr. N. N. Ghosh for microanalysis.

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Received March 26, 1946.